

EDUCATION AND HUMAN CAPITAL DEVELOPMENT FACTORS IN ESTABLISHING THE SOCIAL STATE

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Saidkulov Nuriddin Akramkulovich

Gulistan State Pedagogical Institute,

Associate Professor of the Department of "Social Sciences and Art Studies".

Phone number: +998 97 340 22 99

Orcid: <https://orcid.org/0009-0002-7400-7451>

E-mail: nuriddinsaidkulov89@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

This article talks about reforms in the educational system and their importance. The country will develop and progress only if the education system is set up correctly, and the main attention will be paid to intellectual knowledge. Through intellectual knowledge, the human capital of the country develops. Where human capital is developed, population welfare increases.

Key words: family, neighborhood, education, training, human capital, intellectual knowledge, Third Renaissance.

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada mamlakatda amalga oshirilayotgan ta'lim-tarviya tizimidagi islohotlar hamda ularning ahamiyati haqida so'z boradi. Ta'lim-tarbiya tizimi to'g'ri yo'lga qo'yilsagina mamlakat rivojlanadi, taraqqiy etadi hamda asosiy e'tibor intellektual bilimga qaratiladi. Intellektual bilim orqali esa mamlakatda inson kapitali rivojlanadi. Inson kapitali rivojlangan joyda aholi farovonligi ortadi.

Kalit so'zlar: oila, mahalla, ta'lim, tarbiya, inson kapitali, intellektual bilim, Uchinchi Renessans.

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье говорится о реформах в системе образования и их значении. Страна будет развиваться и прогрессировать только в том случае, если система образования будет построена правильно и основное внимание будет уделяться интеллектуальным знаниям. Через интеллектуальные знания развивается человеческий капитал страны. Там, где развивается человеческий капитал, повышается благосостояние населения.

Ключевые слова: семья, соседство, образование, обучение, человеческий капитал, интеллектуальные знания, Третье Возрождение.

INTRODUCTION

Today, in general, the traditional education and upbringing processes in our educational system are being replaced by innovative methods that are considered the basis of their development. Innovation means innovation. This is interpreted in terms of quality and efficiency. When innovation is applied to education, innovative education means the use of promising methods and tools in educational processes.

When it comes to innovative and creative thinking, paying attention to the "intellectual potential" that is part of it is of great theoretical and methodological importance. Innovative culture refers to the ability of society and individuals to freely create innovations based on the laws of succession. Innovative culture is a set of knowledge and abilities that comprehensively master and apply innovations in various fields of human activity.

METHODS

The diversity of the results of research on human capital affects the quality and scope of research conducted on the evaluation of the role of human capital in the innovative development of the economy.

The first group of studies carried out on the role of human capital in ensuring the socio-economic development of the society includes scientific studies based on the scope and quality of the influence of human capital on the production volume. Among such studies, Romer, 1990 ; Barro, 1991; Temrl, 1999; Kruger and Lindahl, 2001; Works by scholars such as De la Fuente and Dominique, 2005 can be included. At this point, it is clearly visible that in most studies there is a significant positive relationship between human capital and economic growth (R. Solow 1992). Among the researches of the second group, it is possible to include the research results of scientists such as Barro, Kalayzidakis and Hodjo, who served to reveal the direct statistical impact of human capital on innovative development (non-linear and indirect).

Wittstein, in his 1800s work, like Farr, describes them as "capital goods." Individuals claim that their lifetime earnings are the sum of their living and education expenses.

Wittstein's definition of human capital in the 1800s led to the pioneering of human capital theory in the 1960s. Marshall evaluated labor as synonymous with the concept of human capital; "Your most valuable investment," he said, "is an investment in people." Marshall (1890); Similarly, Farr and Petty view human capital as a means of increasing the well-being of the country, not just the well-being of the individual.

LITERATURE REVIEW

In contrast to intellectual resources, intellectual potential means a set of intellectual and creative capabilities, which are often hidden, although not officially recorded, are considered the real basis for the implementation of behavior. Consequently, for the subject to perform a certain activity, to have a set of functions of performing, implementing, performing actions, that is, a set of separate, complex mental behaviors that ensure gradualism in learning the subject of mental work must. Therefore, personal knowledge always requires intellectual capacity and ability. It is not only the presence of knowledge, but also the person, man, individual who is trying to know, understand, his interest in knowledge, his individual, personal approach to the interpretation and analysis of knowledge and its effective and beneficial use, understanding it in a unique and appropriate way. understanding becomes embodied [1.18].

Determining the role of human capital in ensuring the sustainable development of the national economy, creating appropriate conditions for its effective use, is one of the important directions of scientific research in terms of ensuring the country's place in the international community, decent living and sustainable development of the population. does.[2.172] In this regard, it is important to research the impact of the level of development of human capital on economic growth in scientific research, to evaluate the interaction of the structural elements of human capital, to determine the impact on the introduction and spread of innovations, to research effective methods of human capital development.

The main goal of human capital development is:

- development of research of conceptual bases of human capital;
 - summarizing theoretical considerations on the content and structural elements of human capital;
 - by analyzing the evolution of human capital during historical development, revealing its ideological foundations in different periods;
 - to determine the level of its development based on the study of forms of human capital in modern society;
 - To express the main characteristics of human capital in Uzbekistan, its functions and the resources that allow its development;
 - to identify the factors affecting the quality of human capital and research methodological issues of their evaluation;
 - promotes issues such as researching the methodological foundations of the connection between the development of human capital and innovative development.
- The scientific significance is manifested in the research of the laws of the development of mutual relations from the point of view of the processes

characteristic of the new era, as well as in the determination of the place of use in everyday and scientific activities.

Modern technologies develop the education system by promoting thinking, innovative approach and innovation and creativity. Therefore, the development of the educational system is directly related to innovative changes. It is appropriate if innovative changes are focused on the following aspects of the educational system:

- the purpose, content, method and methodology of education, technical-technological aspect, form and method of organization and management system and structural composition;

- material supply and material-technical base and specific incentives in pedagogical educational (student) activities;

- innovative methods in the system of control and assessment of types and levels of education;

- organization of pedagogical and educational process and educational-methodical support;

- to the correct organizational system of educational work in the educational system;

- the innovative nature of the curriculum and educational programs;

- depends on the activity of the student and the teacher and on the strictness of the discipline.

Nevertheless, the following factors hinder the innovative and creative development of a person, especially young people:

1. Avoiding taking risks (that is, not trying your luck, or fearing challenges and trials to achieve results).

2. Not being tactful in thinking and relationships.

3. Lack of appreciation of personal fantasy.

4. Not being independent, but dependent on others.

5. Always thinking only about winning.

6. The existence of hesitation in most cases when starting a job.

7. Lack of logical thinking and avoidance of communication with people.

8. The existence of a situation of underestimating one's knowledge and talent.

9. Believing and following other opinions as a result of not having an independent opinion.

10. A one-sided view during one's activity is only a high confidence in one's own rightness.

11. Factors such as the fear of making mistakes before starting a job prevent innovative and creative development in young people and contribute to a decrease in self-confidence. Therefore, protecting young people from the influence of such

factors has a positive effect on their innovative and creative activity. Their intellectual potential creates a foundation for creating a set of intellectual and creative possibilities.[3.458]

The use of modern advanced pedagogical technologies in the educational system is an important factor in the development of society. That is, the investment directed to the development of the country is the investment aimed at the education of young people, which is the most objective fact proven by historical development. In this sense, the bold step into the Third Renaissance of the new Uzbekistan depends on the intellectual potential, talent and ability of young people who have mastered modern knowledge and matured in all aspects. According to scientific analysis and research, the investment spent on a person between the ages of 3 and 22 will bring 19-22 times more profit in the future.

Therefore, fundamental reforms and changes are continuously being carried out in the education system, which is the basis of all reforms in Uzbekistan. At the same time, the amount of spending on education, including the social sphere, is more than half of the total cost of the state budget. Evaluating these expenses not as an expense, but as an investment for the future, the quality and level of education is the main factor that determines the development of the state. The diversity of the results of research on human capital affects the quality and scope of research conducted on the evaluation of the role of human capital in the innovative development of the economy.

The first group of studies carried out on the role of human capital in ensuring the socio-economic development of the society includes scientific studies based on the scope and quality of the influence of human capital on the production volume. Among such studies, Romer, 1990 ; Barro, 1991; Temrl, 1999; Kruger and Lindahl, 2001; Works by scholars such as De la Fuente and Dominique, 2005 can be included. At this point, it is clearly visible that in most studies there is a significant positive relationship between human capital and economic growth (R. Solow 1992). Among the researches of the second group, it is possible to include the research results of scientists such as Barro, Kalayzidakis and Hodjo, who served to reveal the direct statistical impact of human capital on innovative development (non-linear and indirect).[4.16]

Determining the role of human capital in ensuring the sustainable development of the national economy, creating appropriate conditions for its effective use, is one of the important directions of scientific research in terms of ensuring the country's place in the international community, decent living and sustainable development of the population. does. In this regard, it is important to research the impact of the level of development of human capital on economic growth in scientific research, to

evaluate the interaction of the structural elements of human capital, to determine the impact on the introduction and spread of innovations, to research effective methods of human capital development.[5.172]

In fact, the effectiveness of the ongoing reforms depends, first of all, on the level of personnel and how well they can meet the requirements of the time. Therefore, the system of school education in our country was completely reformed and 11-year general secondary education was restarted. New higher education institutions, scientific and creative centers are being established. Places for admission to higher educational institutions are increasing every year. Correspondence and evening forms of special higher education have been restored. In the next two years, branches of prestigious universities of about 20 developed countries were opened. Academic and financial independence was granted to 35 higher educational institutions this year.

CONCLUSION

Practical work on the development of an effective, targeted system that covers children from birth to the age of 30 in the educational system of our country and helps them find their rightful place in life is being conducted. In this process, it is planned to mobilize all opportunities for our children to be raised as physically and spiritually healthy, people-loving and patriotic people.

In a word, to create modern, comfortable, advanced, creative and innovative conditions for young people to receive education, acquire a profession, and become well-rounded people. Uzbekistan is making full use of its existing capabilities. The main goal is to create the basis of the Third Renaissance, to make innovative and creatively thinking enterprising young people the drivers of the new Uzbekistan so that our country becomes one of the most developed countries in the world.

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